

AN ELLIPTICAL CONSTRUCTION

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Annotation: The article reveals through examples and rates that an Elliptical construction is a sentence in which one or more words are dropped for brevity, this inaction is also called elision, the meaning of an abbreviated sentence should still be clear based on the surrounding context.

Key words: elliptical construction, sentence, shortened sentence, 'omission'....

An elliptical construction is a sentence from which one or more words are omitted for the sake of conciseness. This act of omission is also called elision. The meaning of the shortened sentence should still be clear, however, based on the surrounding context.

In linguistics, ellipsis (from Greek: ἔλλειψις, élleipsis 'omission') or an elliptical construction is the omission from a clause of one or more words that are nevertheless understood in the context of the remaining elements. There are numerous distinct types of ellipsis acknowledged in theoretical syntax.

Ellipsis is the narrative device of omitting a portion of the sequence of events, allowing the reader to fill in the narrative gaps. Aside from its literary use, the ellipsis has a counterpart in film production. It is there to suggest an action by simply showing what happens before and after what is observed.

Elliptical writing occurs when an author opts to not describe an event literally. Instead the writer implies it obliquely—which can be more artful than spelling it out.

The ellipsis mark indicates that you left some material out of a direct quote. It consists of three spaced periods with a space before and after each one .

The analysis of ellipsis is the study of omitting process to some structural slots of unnecessary information to achieve effective either writing or speaking. Ellipsis can be grouped into nominal, verbal, and clausal. dialogue. The research finding shows that ellipsis widely occurs within the dialogue.

Some examples of elliptical clauses would be the following: Harriet has more musical training than Taylor. No one ate more sugar cookies than I. Jasmyn's brother was more excited to go to the football game than she.

The Elliptical sentence is a short form of sentence with some excerpts, but it ends up having the same meaning. It is used to prevent and avoid unnecessary repetition of words.

Proper use does not require that all sentences shall remain completed. It often allows and sometimes requires the omission of words which, although necessary in construction, are so easily provided by the mind that it would be a waste of time to pronounce them.

Here are some examples of elliptical constructions. We will use them for our further understanding on both an elliptical sentence and an elliptical clause.

Types of Elliptical Construction

These three structures comprise the principal types of elliptical construction:

A noun ellipsis removes a noun from a sentence. For instance: "I did a full homework, and May did too". This sentence removes the phrase "a full homework" from its second independent clause. So the sentence is not diminishing the understanding.

A verb ellipsis omits a verb from a sentence. For instance: I drank water and Frale Milk. The verb "drank" appears only once but it refers to both "I" and "Frale".

A verb phrase ellipsis omits an entire phrase that's anchored by a verb. For instance: "I went to the park, but Jim did not". We know that the thing Jim did do was "do to the park", but we omit it as part of this elliptical construction. The meaning of the sentence remained same.

Examples on Elliptical Sentences:

No one ate more sugar cookies than I.

Marine brother was more excited to go to the football game than she.

The pop quiz did not worry my classmates as much as me.

My dogs are jealous that the new kitten is getting more attention than they.

I like him better than Neon does

This racket is not so heavy as that

I have more confidence in Bains than is Ralf

Friam is younger than Luk

Gron likes you better than me

You like him better than I do

Elliptical sentences are such sentences in which one or several parts are felt as missing compared with analogous sentences where there is no ellipsis.

Elliptical sentences may freely be changed into complete sentences:

Nobody in the room, nobody in the corridor — There was nobody in the room, there was nobody in the corridor.

The missing part of an elliptical sentence may be supplied:

From the preceding or following context:

I sat near the window, he — near the door.

From the context of the sentence itself:

I ran after him, but he — over the garden wall.

By means of intonation:

Playing, children? (= are you playing, children?)

But: playing children (playing is an attribute to children).

The following parts of the sentence may be omitted: Subject:

See you to-morrow. Much obliged to you. (Galsworthy.) And he had spoken of Thornfield as my home — would that it were my home! (Bronte.) (= I wish it were my home)

Predicate:

Verb a 1 p r e d i c a t e:

Nobody under the table, nobody under the sofa. (Dickens.) ...days passed like hours, and weeks like days. (Brontë.) ...she liked to inform, I to question... (Bronte.)

Sometimes part of the verbal predicate is omitted:

Having by this time cried as much as I possibly could, I began to think it was of no use crying any more... (Dickens.)

L i n k - v e r b:

It was a lovely afternoon, warm; the sea calm and blue. (Galsworthy.) The sky was blue to the very horizon, and the sea wonderful... (Galsworthy.) His eyes were golden brown, his hair dark auburn... (Maurier.)

Predicative:

“Are you well?” — “I believe I am”. (Брон1ë.) “I am no judge of music, but Mr. Rochester is... (Брон1ë.)

The predicative is often omitted in comparative clauses:

They were both more accomplished and better read than I was... (Брон1ë.)

The auxiliary verb of an analytical form is sometimes omitted in sentences with two or more predicates:

“You will wait and see papa,” said Agnes, cheerfully, “and pass the day with us?” (Dickens.) ...she was playing on, and looking at me with her own calm smile. (Dickens.)

Also in elliptical inscriptions:

English spoken here. Smoking strictly prohibited. The same subject continued (or: continued on page).

The sign outside the factory read: No Hands Wanted. (Hardy.)

Object:

The object is often omitted in short sentences after the verbs to do, to forget, to know, to tell, especially in lively speech:

Don't you know her address? — No, I forget. “What did she want?”—“I don't know.” (Galsworthy.)

Sometimes several parts of the sentence are omitted, especially in answer to a question or in lively speech: “Where is he?” — “In the picture-gallery.” (Galsworthy.) “And when are you going” — “On Monday.” (Galsworthy.) “You are late.” — “Only five minutes.” (Lawrence.) “The exact address, please.” (Greene.) “Well, and what did they say to you?” — “Nothing.” (Galsworthy.) “How was she?” — “Very well.” (Galsworthy.)

The sentence is elliptical when only an auxiliary verb is repeated in answer to a question:

“You will repent to say that, Miss Forsyte.” — “Oh, no,” said June, “I shan't.” (Galsworthy.) “Do you like this sunrise, Jane?” — “I do, very much.” (Bronte.)

The repetition of an auxiliary at the end of a sentence in disjunctive questions is also an elliptical construction:

“Thornfield is a pleasant place in summer, is it not?” (Brontë.) “We have been good friends, Jane, have we not?” (Brontë.)

Elliptical structures are a wonderful way to avoid repeating words. They can make your statements more natural or more complex. But they can also reduce clarity if used incorrectly. The main problem with elliptical structures is that they depend on an absent part of a sentence being understood by the listener.

If parts of the sentence do not agree – for example, the subject and implied verb do not agree – then the sentence can become unclear.

Elliptical: I did four laps around the track, and Marcella did [four laps around the track] too. A verb ellipsis omits a repeated verb from a sentence: Full: I ate steak, and Jennifer ate fish.

Elliptical: I ate steak, and Jennifer, [ate] fish.

Elliptical constructions help us provide complicated information in a clear and concise manner. This is because the Earth has a slightly elliptical orbit around the Sun. This

discrepancy is because of the elliptical orbit of the Earth around the Sun. With its big elliptical wings, and that beautiful soundtrack, it was dashing.

An elliptical clause is a type of dependent, or subordinate, clause that is missing a word or words. Often, the missing part is a verb or verb phrase. While elliptical clauses are acceptable to use, they can sometimes cause confusion for writers and readers, especially when the sentence ends with a pronoun.

Elliptical sentences often appear as one of three main types: noun ellipsis, verb ellipsis, or verb-phrase ellipsis.

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